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Usmanov Muxriddin Abdimuratovich

Doctoral student at the National University of Uzbekistan

Annotation. *This article describes the main features of mythology in the way people think. Furthermore, the ontological aspects of mythology are revealed. It also treats the main role of modern mythology that has been interpreted by various thinkers.*

Keywords: *mythology, mythological, consciousness, myth rhetoric, unity of chaos and space, collective consciousness, human thinking, science and mythology, living myth, mythopoetic view of the universe, rationality.*

As we know, the myth as a social ontological phenomenon is a real phenomenon. The idea that a myth retains the traces of social information about the human society that created it and that an outside observer has the ability to reconstruct that society can only be true in a methodological context and in the context of an abstraction of the existing social situation. It reflects the ability of the human mind to draw conclusions about the unknown from the known, but it says nothing about what happens when an individual belongs to the social world, when he is a part of it. A living myth is not a sign of society because a myth (in most cases) is not created for an outside observer. As S. V. Tikhonova puts it: "People do not study the myths they believe in, but believe in them and organize their lives according to the instructions given in them and act on them." Our task is to understand how this process works.

According to J. Shyopflin, "the main thing in a myth is content, not consistency with historical facts". Furthermore, by choosing an exit point to begin the creation of a myth, the mythological consciousness selects a specific event for itself from a linear chronological context, deleting its cause-and-effect relationships and establishing its own coordinate system. Myth rhetoric is, to a certain extent, fate rhetoric, because myth is invariant, in which a particular event is given an ontological status, requires it to be accepted as a real reality, and does not allow it to be given either rational or rational grounds for the event - according to him what happened "happened as it should"; in the mythopoetic view of the universe, everything is predetermined, just as the two mythical beginnings — the unity of Chaos and the Cosmos and the struggle between them — are marked. Thus, Pushkin's line "Emotion everywhere is destiny, and there is no escape from destiny" can be seen as a methodological principle of myth cosmology.

Through myths, philosophers explained the structure of society and the role of man in it. In the traditions of ancient thinkers, myths formed the worldview of entire nations and states, and this was made possible by the religious and mystical ideas about the universe, nature, society, the activities of gods and heroes in myths.

The influence of myths on the modern human mind has led philosophers to take a unique approach to explaining mythology and defining its essence. Myths are used by modern man and society to correct their behavior and gain direction in the universe. In addition, the deep interest of modern scientists and philosophers in the mythologization of man and society is also determined by the current state of classical science and classical rationality, which directs them to address the following issues:

1. To determine the essence and peculiarities of the mythology of man and society;
2. Identify the system and process by which myths affect society;
3. To study the positive and negative effects of myth on modern culture;
4. Identify commonalities and differences between science and mythology;
5. Develop a vector of possible effects of myths for the further development of society.

From the point of view of science, myth is considered as a universal phenomenon and is studied from the point of view of everyday and philosophical worldview.¹

Twentieth-century scholars and philosophers have analyzed myth as a relatively important phenomenon in the formation of society. It was seen as an event that formed in the collective consciousness and encompassed such areas of state activity as politics, religion, science and philosophy. According to S. A. Khrapov, collective consciousness changes and is formed in a unique way, that is, in both society and culture, based on the interaction of "mythological" and "modern" elements.²

One of the main sources of the formation of myths in the collective consciousness is the media, the Internet, television and the like. In our opinion, there are criteria that define the myths that shape a society's worldview. These are:

1. The belief of the subject who created the myth;
2. The structure of the myth and the essence of its impact on the object.

One of the most common means of spreading myth is the appeal to man himself, his social and subjective needs. This "appeal" is associated with various subjects of influence on a person, including the social environment to which the person belongs, historical conditions, the level of a person's worldview, the level of his material well-being. These are external conditions that allow myth to affect human perception. They change naturally, and this is the result of a residual phenomenon of the historical memory of the myth, its perception by the individual and society as a whole.

In addition, in political activity and public organizations also accept myths to their ideologies, however, they change these myths according to their own organizational forms and formed ideologies. All these changes will have a significant impact on the structure of the state and the future domestic and foreign policy of the state.

In our opinion, myths are formed in the course of their development in the following direction:

¹ Барт Р. Мифологии / Барт Ролан; перевод с французского, вступительная статья, комментарии С.Зенкина. – М.: Академический проект, 2008. 138 с.

² Храпов С. А. Трансформация сознания российского общества в контексте социально-экономической динамики потребления // Власть. – 2010. – № 2. – С. 56-58.

1. Myth has a psychologically stable effect on the daily consciousness of man;
2. The subject affected by the myth undergoes a stage of consciousness at the subconscious level, which in turn leads to a violation of the ideology of the person (in positive or negative directions).

Since myth is the central concept of the mythological landscape of the world, then the essence of the myth determines the essence of the mythological landscape of the world in the future, and distinguishes different forms of the mythological landscape of the world based on the classification of the mythological essence. These include: etiological, prayer-related, cosmogonic and cosmological, theogonic, anthropological, astral (solar and lunar), calendar, ethical, heroic, totemic, thanatologic, eschatological, and others.

This landscape is characterized by the fact that it allows direct coding of information through a certain tradition adopted within this social product, which in turn is based on ancient cosmogonic and mythological notions of man and is based on similar or "false" objects, objects or events. The legend also has a unique, distinct mythological time and mythological space. An example of this is the fact that the researcher V.M.Naydysh showed that mythological time can be described as some kind of distant past, completely different from today, the modern period.

In turn, the mythological past manifests itself as a model, i.e., an example of modern events that occur in a manner similar to the events of a long mythological period. In this case, mythological time passes into mythological space, and vice versa. The mythological space is the space of life passed down from generation to generation, the part of the world in which this generation originated and lives because of a certain totem (hereditary symbol), in other words, a seed elder who manifests as something (animal, plant or inorganic object).

The life span of the seed and its totem determine the mythological space of the seed. The forces that gave rise to this seed have not yet disappeared, they still exist, and man believes that the space of physical things that surrounds him can pass into the space of totem forces that in the past created man himself, his offspring, his seed (including death to life and life to death). Thus, the system of mythological interpretation is based on the belief in the authenticity of the phenomena of myth, mythological time and space. This means that the myth did not need to be examined and substantiated as an understanding of any world.

Myth has a great influence on the policy of the state and the social sphere of society in its period of change. Thus, the main role of the myth can be determined by its etymological content, and this content is perceived by its affected subjects. According to A.D. Vasilev, “the most effective way to create this type of myth is the purposeful use of precedent verbal symbols, such as the names of historical figures, literary heroes, chronotoponyms-symbols (for example, military conflict names). they must be well known to a particular ethnic unit, have played an important role in the formation of historical memory, and must be involved in linking different generations together.”³

³ Васильев А. Д. Современное мифотворчество и российская телевизионная словесность. – М.: ЛЕНАНД, 2014. 10 с.

New conditions constantly create new myths, or reshape the negative ones, and thus adapt to new mythological, and ideological constructions. There is a process of penetration of myths into various political and social structures, and thus the myths become a "legitimate" reality.

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